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ABSTRACT BOOK

IMPACT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON INITIATION OF ANTIHYPERTENSIVES IN SWEDEN- AN INTERRUPTED TIME SERIES STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Background

Hypertension is a risk factor for Covid-19, and adequate antihypertensive treatment is of importance. Restrictions during the pandemic limited access to healthcare, which may have had a negative impact on drug prescribing.

Aims

Assessing the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on initiation of antihypertensive drugs in Sweden.

Methods

Data on dispensed prescriptions of diuretics, beta-blockers (BB), calcium channel blockers (CCB), angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors (ACEi) and angiotensin receptor blockers (ARB) were extracted from the SCIFI-PEARL database linking national registers on drugs and diseases for the entire Swedish population March 2018-November 2021. Interrupted time series analysis was conducted using an autoregressive (ARIMA) model. Monthly cumulative incidence was calculated based on number of patients initiating each drug class after a one-year washout period.

Results

The analysis included 720300 patients. The start of the pandemic was associated with an immediate statistically significant level decrease in initiation of any antihypertensive, followed by a 0.02-0.06% monthly increase, in both sexes. A significant level decrease was observed for ACEi in both sexes and for all classes except diuretics in patients >65 years. A significant post intervention trend change was observed for initiation of diuretics overall (0.013%), driven mainly by a significant increase in patients >65 years. Similar trend differences were also observed for diuretics in females (0.02%) and ACEi (0.03%) in patients >65 years.

Conclusions

The pandemic had an immediate short-term effect, but we found no major adverse influence of the COVID-19 pandemic on initiation with antihypertensive drugs.